

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Mulugeta****FIRST NAME: Addis****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord MacBook Air

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. What are the three main structures of any kind of essay?**
 - Introduction, body and conclusion.¹**
 - Topic sentence, evidence and analysis.
 - Topic sentence, supporting sentences and body
 - Topic sentence, supporting sentences and conclusion

- 2. There are three kinds of questions that researchers ask. These are; conceptual, practical and applied questions. Which one of the following type of questions express conceptual, practical and applied questions?**
 - What should we think? What should we do? What muss we understand before we know what to do?²**

¹ Laurent Cleanewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

- What are your claim? What are your reasons? What evidence support your reasons?
 - What about other point of view? What principles makes your reasons relevance?
 - What is your claim? What reasons support it? What evidence support those reasons?
3. **There are at least four reasons to cite your sources. Which one of the following is not correct about citing your sources?**
- To give writers credit.
 - To assure readers about the accuracy of your facts.
 - To give classmate and family recognition.³**
 - To help readers follow or extend your research.
4. **Which one of the following is true about the Bibliography style citation?**
- Used in most social and natural as well as physical sciences
 - You signal that you have used a source by placing parenthetical citation.
 - You signal that you have used a source by placing superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it.⁴**
 - At the end of the paper, your list all sources in a reference list.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013).

³ Turabian, 86.

⁴ Turabian, 87–88.

5. **The order of elements in notes and bibliography entries follows the same general pattern for all types of sources: author, title and facts of publication. Which one of the following is true about note citing?**

- Notes presents authors' names in standard order (first name first).⁵**
- Notes presents authors' names in standard order (last name first).
- Notes citing specific passages doesn't include page number.
- Notes citing specific passages doesn't include other location information.

6. **Methods of data collection. What are the instruments of qualitative research methods of data collection.**

- Survey includes closed-ended questions.
- Scales, ranking order checklists
- Instruments yield performance data, observational data, census data.
- Interviews, documents, focus group, and critical incidents.⁶**

7. **Dissertation process or the cyclical qualitative dissertation process**

- Reading, conducting study, collecting and managing data, writing, analyzing data and reporting findings, interpreting and synthesizing findings and developing conclusions and recommendations.
- Reading, writing, planning, conducting study, collecting and managing data, interpreting and synthesizing findings and developing conclusions and recommendations and analyzing data and reporting findings.

⁵ Turabian, 92.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Second (Thousand Oaks, Calif: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2012), 14.

- Reading, analyzing data and report findings, writing, planning, conducting study, collecting and managing data, interpreting and synthesizing findings and developing conclusions and recommendations.
- Reading, planning, writing, conducting study, collecting and managing data, analyzing data and reporting findings, interpreting and synthesizing findings and developing conclusions and recommendations.**⁷

8. **Who can we write the title of member of European Commission?**

- Mr. X, president of the commission...
- Mr. X, President of the Commission...**⁸
- Mr. X, President of the commission...
- Mr. x, president of the Commission...

9. **Which one of the following is a primary source for evidence?**

- Books and articles.
- General encyclopedias and dictionaries.
- Original works- like diaries.**⁹
- Newspapers and magazines.

10. **Once you assemble your argument, you might be ready for what?**

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 1.

⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General, English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission, 8th ed. (European Union, 2020), 62.

⁹ Turabian, 24.

- To draft.**¹⁰
- Presenting evidence in tables and figures
- Write your final introduction
- Write your first conclusion

¹⁰ Turabian, 43.

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